

Studies in the Synthesis of Coumarino- α -pyrones and Furocoumarins. Part XX*. Synthesis of Furo(3, 2-*c*) benzopyran and Furo(3, 2-*f*) benzopyran Derivatives

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4-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-8-methylcoumarin on Pechmann condensation with ethyl acetoacetate gave 4,7-dimethyl-8-methoxy-2,5-dioxo-2*H*,5*H*-pyrano(3,2-*c*)benzopyran (Ia) which on bromination hydrolysis and subsequent cyclisation gave 3,6-dimethyl-7-methoxy-4-oxo-4*H*-furo(3,2-*c*) benzopyran (III). 2-Hydroxy-5-allyloxy-acetophenone (IVb) when treated with diethyl carbonate and sodium gave (Va) which on methylation and Claisen rearrangement gave (Vc). This was cyclised to (VI) which on dehydrogenation and subsequent demethylation gave 4-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-oxo-6*H*-furo(3,2-*f*)benzopyran (VIIIb). This on treatment with formaldehyde gave (VIII).

IN continuation of our work on furocoumarins^{1,2}, we report here the synthesis of 3,6-dimethyl-7-methoxy-4-oxo-4*H*-furo(3,2-*c*) benzopyran and 4-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-oxo-6*H*-furo(3,2-*f*)benzopyran.

4-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-8-methylcoumarin on Pechmann condensation with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride afforded 4,7-dimethyl-8-methoxy-2,5-dioxo-2*H*, 5*H*-pyrano(3, 2-*c*) benzopyran (Ia). This on bromination gave 3-bromo derivative (Ib) which was hydrolysed by sodium carbonate to 2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-methyl-4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-methylfuran-3-carboxylic acid (II). This hydroxy acid on cyclisation with conc. hydrochloric acid gave 3,6-dimethyl-7-methoxy-4-oxo-4*H*-furo(3,2-*c*)benzopyran (III).

2,5-Dihydroxyacetophenone (IVa) was refluxed with allyl bromide in acetone to obtain 2-hydroxy-5-allyloxyacetophenone (IVb). It was then treated with sodium and diethyl carbonate³ on water bath to give 4-hydroxy-2-allyloxy coumarin (Va) which was subsequently methylated to 4-methoxy-6-allyloxy coumarin (Vb). This methyl ether on Claisen rearrangement in dimethyl aniline afforded 4-methoxy-6-hydroxy-5-allylcoumarin (Vc), the structure of which was confirmed by NMR spectrum (CDCl₃), δ 9.6, one proton singlet, hydroxylic proton disappears on exchange with D₂O, δ 7.15, two protons singlet H₇ and H₈, δ 6.25-5.9, one proton multiplet = CH, δ 5.8, one proton singlet H₃, δ 5.1 and δ 4.8, two proton doublet = CH₂, the latter showing a barely visible long range coupling ($J = 1$ Hz), δ 3.98, three protons singlet -OCH₃ group, δ 3.8, two protons doublet = CH-CH₂.

This allylcoumarin was cyclised to 4-methoxy-2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-6-oxo-6*H*-furo(3,2-*f*) benzopyran (VI) by triturating it with conc. sulphuric acid. The structure of which was confirmed by NMR spectrum (CDCl₃); δ 7.0 and δ 6.8, two one proton doublets,

$J = 8$ Hz; H₈ and H₉; δ 5.6, one proton singlet H₅, δ 5.18-4.8, one proton multiplet H₂; δ 3.9, three protons singlet—OCH₃ group, δ 3.7-2.8, two protons multiplet H₃; δ 1.45 three protons doublet 2-CH₃ group. It was then dehydrogenated with palladised charcoal by refluxing in diphenyl ether to 4-methoxy-2-methyl-6-oxo-6*H*-furo(3,2-*f*) benzopyran (VIIa) and subsequently demethylated by boiling with conc. hydrochloric acid to 4-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-oxo-6*H*-furo(3,2-*f*)benzopyran (VIIb). When this furocoumarin was refluxed with formaldehyde solution in alcohol it gave 5,5'-methylene bis(4-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-oxo-6*H*-furo(3,2-*f*)benzopyran (VIII).

Experimental

NMR spectra were recorded on Varian A 60 spectrophotometer and DMSO-d₆ was used as solvent, using TMS as internal indicator.

4,7-Dimethyl-8-methoxy-2,5-dioxo-2*H*, 5*H*-pyrano(3, 2-*c*) benzopyran (Ia): A mixture of 4-hydroxy-7-methoxy-8-methylcoumarin (5.0 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (10 ml) was added slowly to a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (6.5 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (30 ml.) and was heated in an oil bath at 130°-40° for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and nitrobenzene was steam distilled. The product was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 238°. Yield 4.3 g. (Found: C, 66.47; H, 4.37. C₅H₁₂O₅ requires: C, 66.17; H, 4.44%).

3-Bromo-4,7-dimethyl-8-methoxy-2,5-dioxo-2*H*, 5*H*-pyrano(3,2-*c*)benzopyran (Ib): 4,7-Dimethyl-8-methoxy-2,5-dioxo-2*H*, 5*H*-pyrano(3,2-*c*)benzopyran (2.5 g.) was dissolved in hot acetic acid and to the hot solution was added bromine in acetic acid (8 ml.; 20%; 1 mole) was added with stirring. The product

which separated immediately was filtered, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 250°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found: Br, 22.76; C₁₅H₁₁O₅Br, requires: Br, 22.79%).

2-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-methyl-4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-methylfuran-3-carboxylic acid (II): 3-Bromo-4,7-dimethyl-8-methoxy-2,5-dioxo-2H, 5H-pyrano(3,2-c) benzopyran (1.0 g.) was refluxed with sodium carbonate

treated with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and crystallised from water, m.p. 216°. Yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 63.63; H, 5.15. C₁₄H₁₄O₅ requires: C, 64.11; H, 5.38%).

3,6-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-4-oxo-4H-furo (3,2-c) benzopyran (III): 2-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-methyl-4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-methylfuran-3-carboxylic acid (0.5 g.) was dissolved in ethanol (5 ml.) and refluxed with

I
a, R=H
b, R=Br

II

IV

a, R=H
b, R=-CH₂-CH=CH₂

V

a, R=R₂=H; R₁=-CH₂-CH=CH₂
b, R=CH₃; R₁=-CH₂-CH=CH₂; R₂=H
c, R=CH₃; R₁=H; R₂=-CH₂-CH=CH₂

VI

VII

a, R=CH₃
b, R=H

VIII

solution (10 ml.; 10%) for 5 hr. This reaction mixture was cooled and acidified. The product was filtered,

hydrochloric acid (10 ml.) for 3 hr. The separated product was filtered (charcoal), washed with sodium

bicarbonate solution and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 160°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found : C, 68.42; H, 5.21. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 68.84; H, 4.95%).

4-Hydroxy-6-allyloxy coumarin (Va) : A mixture of 2-hydroxy-5-allyloxyacetophenone (4.0 g.), diethyl carbonate (20 ml.) and pulverised sodium (3.0 g.) was heated on a water bath for 2 hr. The unreacted sodium was decomposed with little alcohol and the reaction mixture was poured into water. It was extracted with ether and aqueous layer was acidified. The separated product was filtered, treated with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 221°. Yield 3.5 g. (Found : C, 65.63; H, 4.26. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires : C, 66.05; H, 4.62%).

4-Methoxy-6-allyloxy coumarin (Vb) : A mixture of 4-hydroxy-6-allyloxy coumarin (3.5 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (6.0 g.) and dimethyl sulphate (3 ml.) in dry acetone (50 ml.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 6 hr. The product obtained on evaporation of acetone crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 106°. Yield 2.5 g. (Found : C, 67.01; H, 4.84. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.23; H, 5.21%).

4-Methoxy-6-hydroxy-5-allyl coumarin (Vc) : 4-Methoxy-6-allyloxy coumarin (2.0 g.) in dimethyl aniline (6.0 ml.) was refluxed for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was kept overnight and the separated product was filtered, treated with dil. sodium hydroxide solution, dried and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 208°. Yield 1.0 g. (Found : C, 67.20; H, 5.10. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires : C, 67.23; H, 5.21%).

4-Methoxy-2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-6-oxo-6H-furo (3,2-f) benzopyran (VI) : 4-Methoxy-6-hydroxy-5-allyl coumarin (0.8 g.) was triturated with conc. sulphuric acid (3 ml.) for 10 min. The reaction mixture was then decomposed with ice and water. The separated product was filtered, washed with dil. sodium hydroxide solution and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 187°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 66.94; H, 5.29. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.23; H, 5.21%).

4-Methoxy-2-methyl-6-oxo-6H-furo (3,2-f) benzopyran (VIIa) : 4-Methoxy-2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-6-oxo-6H-furo (3,2-f) benzopyran (0.5 g.) was refluxed with palladised charcoal (0.4 g.; 10%) in boiling diphenyl ether (3 ml.) for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and allowed to cool. The separated product was filtered, washed with petroleum ether and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 201°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 67.64; H, 4.32. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4$ requires : C, 67.82; H, 4.38%).

4-Hydroxy-2-methyl-6-oxo-6H-furo (3,2-f) benzopyran (VIIb) : 4-Methoxy-2-methyl-6-oxo-6H-furo (3,2-f) benzopyran (0.3 g.) was dissolved in ethanol (5 ml.) and refluxed with conc. hydrochloric acid (5 ml.) for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and the separated product was filtered, treated with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 295°. Yield 0.1 g. (Found : C, 66.58; H, 3.87. $C_{12}H_8O_4$ requires C, 66.67; H, 3.73%).

5,5'-Methylene bis(4-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-oxo-6H-furo (3,2-f) benzopyran (VIII)) : 4-Hydroxy-2-methyl-6-oxo-6H-furo (3,2-f) benzopyran (0.1 g) was dissolved in ethanol (5 ml.) and refluxed with formaldehyde solution (0.2 ml.) for 30 min. The separated product was filtered hot and dried, m.p. 335°. (Found : C, 67.44; H, 3.44. $C_{25}H_{16}O_8$ requires : C, 67.57; H, 3.63%).

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